

Performance and Characteristic of Nickel Metal Hydride Battery and Charger System for U.S. Army

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ABSTRACT

The US Army has developed a Nickel Metal Hydride (NMH) BB-390 Battery System and a two hour charger for Sincgar radios. It can provide 240 watts (10 Amperes at 24 Volts) of power in the radio's transmit operational mode. The BB-390 battery replaced the BB-590 Nickel Cadmium battery. The BB-390 battery contains 40 "A" size cells and provides up to two times the capacity over the nickel cadmium battery with same weight. During charging of the BB-390 NMH battery, the battery will heat up to as high as 57 degrees C. This NMH battery contains 10 thermal devices for protection during both charge and discharge. It is also protected from external short as well as overdischarge. This evaluation is to verify the NMH battery can exceed the military specification requirement as well as to characterize the boundary conditions for NMH battery.

Introduction

The U. S. Army needs better capacity, safe, and high performance and cost effective, rechargeable batteries to provide power to a wide range of man-portable radio for Project Manager SINCGAR. Over 50 different radios in the current Army inventory can use BB-390/U rechargeable batteries as a cost-effective alternative for nonrechargeable batteries for training, or in some instances as the sole power source. The total demand for BB-390A/U configuration has risen from 100 batteries per year to approximately 7,000 per year. This battery can now be provided 8 hours of service for training. It can provide a great cost savings to the U.S. Army especially in training. This evaluation compared the NMH and nickel cadmium battery test results.

Table 1: BB-390 Nickel Metal Hydride and Nickel Cadmium batteries Configurations.

Battery Type	Alternative Configuration	Capacity (Ah)	Estimated Weight Lbs.
BB-590 (Nid)	20 sub "C _D " size	2-2.3	3.85
BB-390 (12/24V) NMH	1) 40 "A" size (2P)(NMH)	3.6-4.8	3.85
	2) 20 4/3 "A"	3.6-4.8	3.65

Requirements

The preliminary minimum requirements for the BB-390A/U battery are listed below in Table 2

Table 2: Summary the BB-390 requirement

Discharge Rates	5 Second Voltage (V)	Final Voltage (V)	Current (A)
C/5	-	20.0	0.8
C/2	-	20.0	2
C ₅	-	20.0	4.0
2.5C ₅	22.0	20.0	10.0

Charge rate for testing: C or C/2 (2 hours)

Performance Requirement:

Test	Discharge Rate	Capacity Requirement (Ah)
Full Capacity Discharge	C/2	4.0
Cycle Life, 224 cycles	C ₅	3.6
Overcharge, 24 hours	C ₅ /2	4.0
High Rate Discharge	2.5C ₅	3.0
Low Temperature Discharge at -30°C (-22°F)	C ₅ /2	2.6
Retention of charge 7 days at 50°C (122°F)	C ₅ /2	1.3
Pulse Discharge 20 A, 5 seconds on, 25 seconds off, continuously to 10 volts (parallel mode)	5C ₅	6.6
Vibration	C/5	4.0

Experimental

The Army conducted the first article tests and found the BB-390 exceeded the specification in most cases. All batteries were tested and recorded using a MACCOR Battery Cycler and provided by the contractor as a first article test results. The results from the operating time were collected from the MACCOR Battery Cycler using the Singcar radio profiles.

Results and Discussion

Battery performance

Table 3 lists operating times, in hours, at -40 F to 130 F of the discharges with the radio's profiles. Table 4 summarizes the test results from the first article tests. These results indicated the NMH battery exceeded the nickel cadmium battery and provides close to 2 times the service. The most important result is that it can provide 8 hours of service during training. The BB-390 NMH

can be recharged in two hours using the PP-8444/U charger. This charger can recharge two batteries in two hours. Figure 1 below, shows BB-390 discharge curves at 10.8A/7.2A/3.6A/1.8A/.36A to 20 Volts cutoff at 25C. Figure 2 indicates the battery can discharge at 3.6A and still provide 3.41 AH of capacity.

Conclusions

The BB-390/U nickel metal hydride battery was fielded three years ago and it has been demonstrated it can replace the nickel cadmium battery, and in most case, it can also replace lithium sulphur dioxide nonrechargeable battery for training.

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Table 3: Service time in hours for BB390 and Li/SO2 non-rechargeable battery at various temperatures.

		Operating Time in Hours @ indicated temperature for NMH (Li/SO2)				
Radio type	Operating Mode	-40F NMH (LiSO2)	-20F NMH (LiSO2)	-4F NMH (LiSO2)	70F NMH (LiSO2)	130F NMH (LiSO2)
RT-1523 (ITT-COM) SINCGARs	Transmit	0	1.7	1.7 (3.6)	2.3 (5.3)	2.3 (5.3)
	Receive 1T:3R:6S	0	5.7	9.3 (27.6) 6.9 (13.8)	13.2 (26.8) 9.6 (21.0)	13.1 (31.3) 8.7 (21.2)
RT-1523 (GD-COM) (ITT-SIP) SINCGARs	Transmit	0.08	3.6	3.7 (7.0)	4.3 (9.6)	4.0 (9.8)
	Receive 1T:3R:6S	6.3	12.3	15.6/35.8 12.2 (25.4)	17.1 (40.3) 13.7 (31.7)	16.5 (39.6) 13.0 (32)
RT-1547 (PRC-126)	Transmit	1.1	4.25	4.3 (9.9)	4.9 (12.5)	4.5 (13)
	Receive 1T:3R:6S	23.5	26.0	66 (147) 25.5 (65)	64 (152) 28.5 (74)	68 (154) 26 (75)

Table 4 : First Article Test Report for BB-390A/U

TEST	DISCHARGE RATE (A)	CAPACITY REQUIRED FOR NiCAD (AH)	CAPACITY REQUIRED FOR NMH (AH)	CAPACITY RESULT
Fully Capacity	3.6	2.0 @ 2A	3.2	3.9
Cycle Life, 224 cycles	3.6	1.5 @ 2A	2.7	
Overcharge, 24 hours	3.6	2.0 @ 2A	3.2	3.99
High Rate Discharge	10.0	1.2 @ 10A	2.2	2.9
Low Temperature Discharge -20C	2.0	0.8 @ 2A -30C	2.0	3.11
Retention of charge 7 days at 50 C (122F)	3.6	1.2 @2A	1.5	2.06
Pulse Discharge 20 amps, 5S on, 25 S off, to 10V	20 (12 V)	2.4 @36A (12V)	6.0	8.9

BB-390A/U Discharge at 10.8/7.2/3.6/1.8/36A/20V at 25C

BB-390A/U NMH Discharge at -14C at 7.2/3.6/1.8A

